

**Chemical Examination of the Stem bark of
*Diospyros discolor***

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DIOSPYROS discolor is used in the indigenous system of medicine¹. Previous work on this plant have disclosed the presence of β -sitosterol, lupeol, betulin, betulinic acid, tannin glycoside and new anthraquinones^{2,3}. We have reported herein the isolation of a new sterol, identified as stigmasta-5,6-dihydro-22-en-3 β -ol (1) together with betulinic

acid, characterised on the basis of chemical and spectral data.

The sterol (1), m. p. 187–88°, $C_{29}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 414) gave characteristic sterol reactions^{4,5}. The ir spectrum (KBr) showed absorptions at 3 425–3 300 (OH), 3 050, 2 970, 2 870, 1 630 (C=C), 1 420, 1 390, 1 060, 1 020, 970 (double bond), 950, 835 and 800 cm^{-1} , the 1H nmr spectrum ($CDCl_3$, TMS) exhibited signals at δ 5.12 (2H, q J 4 and 8 Hz, C_{22} - and C_{23} -H), 4.40 (1H, m, C-3), 2.35 (1H, s, 1 \times OH), 2.00–1.20 (28H, complex pattern- CH_2 and -CH), 0.95 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, C-21- CH_3), 0.80 (3H, t, J 5 Hz, C-29- CH_3), 0.75 (6H, s, C_{18} - and C_{19} - CH_3) and 0.62 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, C-26 and C-27- CH_3) and the mass spectrum showed fragments at m/z 414 (M^+), 399 (M^+-15), 396 (M^+-18), 381, 370, 302, 301, 289, 275, 261, 259 and 181. Compound 1 formed a monoacetate, $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 121–22°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 720 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.10 (3H, s, $OCOCH_3$) and a benzoate, $C_{38}H_{54}O_2$, m.p. 134–35°, showing the presence of an OH function in the molecule. 1 on Oppenauer oxidation gave stigmasta-5,6-dihydro-22-ene-3- β -one, m.p. 83–84° (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁶ confirming the presence of C-3-OH group. Ozonolysis of 1 gave aldehyde which located the double bond probably at the $\Delta^{22(23)}$ -position⁷. On reduction with PtO_2 -HOAc, 1 afforded stigmastanol, m.p. 135–36° (lit.⁸ 136–37°), identified by comparison (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁸. Thus the new sterol was assigned as stigmasta-5,6-dihydro-22-en-3 β -ol (1) which was also supported by ^{13}C nmr data (20 15 MHz; $CDCl_3$) δ 37.00 (C-1), 31.50 (C-2), 79.90 (C-3), 38.70 (C-4), 56.00 (C-5), 18.50 (C-6), 31.80 (C-7 and C-8), 50.00 (C-9), 36.50 (C-10), 21.00 (C-11), 39.50 (C-12), 42.20 (C-13), 56.75 (C-14), 24.20 (C-15), 28.20 (C-16), 56.00 (C-17), 11.70 (C-18), 19.20 (C-19), 36.00 (C-20), 18.50 (C-21), 120.90 (C-22), 134.20 (C-23), 45.70 (C-24), 29.25 (C-25), 19.80 (C-26) 18.90 (C-27), 23.05 (C-28) and 11.90 (C-29).

Experimental

Air-dried powdered stem bark (3 kg) of *D. discolor* (procured from the United Chemicals and Allied Products, Calcutta) was exhaustively extracted thrice with ethanol. The combined extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to give a viscous mass which was refluxed with petroleum ether and benzene respectively. The C_6H_6 fraction afforded betulinic acid (m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc)³. The petroleum ether fraction was purified over neutral alumina column and eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (6 : 4, v/v) which furnished a colourless crystalline solid (900 mg), m.p. 187–88° ($CHCl_3$) (Found : C, 84.43; H, 12.05. $C_{29}H_{50}O$ requires : C, 84.46; H, 12.07%) homogeneous on tlc, R_f 0.60 (C_6H_6 - $CHCl_3$, 6 : 4 v/v) and 0.84 ($CHCl_3$ - CH_3OH , 9 : 1 v/v). Compound 1 (150 mg) was acetylated with Ac_2O (7 ml) and pyridine (7 ml) and the product was crystallised from ether-methanol mixture as colourless plates, m.p. 121–22° (Found : C, 81.90; H,

12.30. $C_{31}H_{52}O$ requires : C, 81.93; H, 12.32%), 1 (50 mg) was benzyolated with $PhCOCl$ (3 ml) and pyridine (4 ml) to give a product, m.p. 134–35° (Found : C, 83.60; H, 10.40. $C_{38}H_{54}O_2$ requires : C, 83.71; H, 10.42%).

Ozonolysis of 1: Compound 1 (100 mg) in glacial HOAc (10 ml) was ozonised for 2 h at an ozone concentration of 2%, the exit gases being led through H_2O (20 ml). The distillate (20 ml) was collected and a solution of recrystallised *p*- NO_2 -Ph-NHNH₂ (100 mg) in HOAc (10 ml) 50% was gradually added to it. The hydrazone was crystallised from EtOH, m.p. 85–87°. It was identified as α -ethylisovarlardehyde-*p*-nitrophenylhydrazone (lit m.p. 85–88°, tlc and m.m.p.) (Found : C, 62.36; H, 7.80; N, 16.78. $C_{15}H_{20}N_2O_2$ requires : C, 62.40; H, 7.00; N, 16.80%).

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